

**Sujata Parashar's in Pursuit of Ecstasy:
A study in Changing Paradigm of Youths
Deepali Rohit Tade¹ & Sabiha Asif Faras²**

¹Assistant Professor, Department of English, S.B. Khade Mahavidyalaya, Koparde.

²Associate Professor, Department of English, Chandrabai Shantappa Shendure College, Hupari.

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ABSTRACT:

Sujata Parashar is a budding Indian writer in English. She is an award winning Indian writer. Romance, thrill, revenge, suspense, family relationships, social problems, extra marital affairs are the major themes of the Sujata Parashar's novels. The present novel depicts the changing paradigms of youth. Youth are the pillars of our nation. They are our future. But nowadays youths lifestyle changes such as dressing sense, food, alcoholism, drug usage, partying at night, affairs etc. Young generation speaks lie in freely and they don't hesitate taking drugs and alcohols. It declines the value of like truth, simplicity, honesty, loyalty replaced by lie, lust, anger, jealousy. The present novel In Pursuit of Ecstasy is a youthful and engaging story of full of sparkling insights on the lives of urban teenagers today. Aparajita, Deepanita. Aniket and Siddharth have much more in common than being just college mates. All of them either lie or hide things from their parents and want total freedom to follow their dreams. However destiny has other plans for the four youngsters. They encounter drug peddlers who intend to use them as pawns for safely supplying drugs. Their journey from here on makes them question their values, beliefs and desires.

KEYWORDS:

Pursuit, Ecstasy, Youth, Change, Paradigm.

INTRODUCTION:

Change is the law of nature. Change occurs in every walk of life whether it is social, economic, cultural, traditional, technological or personal. Everybody is in mad race they improved their standard of living. This change in life style affects the every type of class and generation in our country; especially it affect the young people or youth. Youth is a major human resource for development of a society. No society can hope of translating it's dreams and vision into reality with the proper utilization of the potential of youth. Today is the age of globalization so there is a great change coming in the lifestyle of youth. This changing paradigms of youth effects the values, culture, beliefs and traditions of young people. Youth are usually referred to as young persons of a nation. In India every third person in Indian city today is youth. Youth being enthusiastic, vibrant, innovative and dynamic in nature. Young generation are the pillars of our nation. They are our future. But nowadays youth's lifestyle paradigms changes such as dressing sense, food, alcoholism, drug usage, partying at night, technology, affairs, nuclear family etc. Also, the change in lifestyle of women conditions in the society is improved. She moves in the outer world freely and this leads to the change in lifestyle of young generation in India. Modern paradigms of youth have a number of effects on health physically, psychologically and socially. The youth of India have been caught in the mood of frustration and confusion and they don't know about the right decision and a result they are often found to indulge in anti-social activities like drug peddling, smuggling. They speaks lie in freely and they don't hesitate taking drugs and alcohols. It is harmful to health and environment. Youth want the live lavish life. They doesn't have any interest in the development of nation and don't ever know what's happening around the world. They are becoming self - Centre.

Sujata Parashar is an award-winning Indian novelist, poet, short story writer and psychological trainer. She is an activist and author of several fictions. Her fictions are suitable for Bollywood movies. She is the recipient of Karam Veer Chakra award. She is representative of Post modern period. The main purpose of this paper is a story brings out the constant tug-of-war between the Indian youth and their aspirations and the parental expectations. This story touches upon the clinched problems of teenagers and their changing paradigms. It is about friendship, introspection and their realization that life's fair to all amidst its turbulences and maze like structure. Scope of this is limited to this novel only. Analytical, interpretative, evaluative approach will be preferred to judge the novel. Here an honest attempt is made to show the writer is successful to relate to the present situation of young generation. Now let's see how the writer Sujata Parashar is successful to depict a tale of today's youth and their outlook towards life.

Sujata Parashar's novel 'In Pursuit of Ecstasy' supposedly is a novel for the youth. It touches upon the clinched problems of teenagers. The story contains a wide mix of characters and the experiences of the six main characters, their lives ups and downs. So, now we have four teenagers (Aparajita or Aupora, Deepanita or Deep, Aniket and Siddharth or Sid) in their degree college who lie and hide things from their rich parents who are either ministers or rich business folk. They view life with multi-layered glasses and have a lot of expectations not only from themselves but also from people around them and top most on the list is to liberate themselves from family bonds and live their own life. The parents of these kids are busy in their own lives and either has no time for them or past has distanced them from their children. Aupora's father who is a cabinet minister does not like his daughter participating in any kind of art especially dance she fancies. Her mother though not as ada-

mant supports her hobby in this aspect. Aupora finds herself coming closer to the domestic help but that does not stop her from lying continuously find ways to enjoy her dream of becoming a choreographer and not an economist as her father wishes. Aparajita is a best liar. For example she speaks lies with professor because she was late for lecture. 'Sir . . . actually my mother had to go to a seminar organized for the school- dropout, adolescent girls on 'the importance of education for a girl child.' She coaxed me into joining her so that I could interact with the girls and share my views on education and why it is so important for a better living.' She said, meeting his gaze directly and secretly proud of her skills.and she also said that being from the same peer group I would have an impact on them. I would have not gone, but she promised me that I would be back on time to attend my classes.' Aparajita paused for air and the Professor's reaction. She got no response but continued. ' . . . errrr . . . you see sir, some people were late for the seminar and everything got delayed. I am sorry sir. Next time, I will not go with her even if she insists.'(IPE.11)

In fact, some of her close friends swore that she is the best liar they had known in their lives. The lies would just tumble out from her mouth like she was telling 'the truth' and 'nothing but the truth'. Deepanita's father heads a company with help from her two elder brothers. Deepa's parents want her to be married off once of being an accountant in her father's firm. Deep also has a huge crush on Aniket, who along with Aupora forms their own little friend circle. Siddharth has the image of a good guy gone bad once we comes to know his life story. Having lost his grandmother who was the only person who loved him. He is torn between the constant busy schedule of his parents, especially his father, who is a scholarly personality and is even invited to his collage to lecture other students occasionally. Sid cant's see eye to eye with Aupora due to

some personal differences but ends up falling in love with her best friend Deepanita. Aniket's father is the minister for art and cultural affairs and has a soft corner for Aupora like his son, who is totally smitten by her. Aniket is hugged by the fact that his mother always nags him and all his father does is talk about himself and so he develops a drinking habit. Ritesh and Sushanto, two brothers who have links with the underworld enter the scene. They are apparently under threat from Lord who is a dreaded don, to buck up their drug peddling business or crumble. Sushanto who disguises as the dance teacher of the college uses the students to come out of his 'drug deficit' for supplying drugs to a 'rave party' in Shimla. 'This is a police raid. Please do not move. The building is surrounded. Stay in your places.' (IPE.253) And then everyone is caught red handed by the police and what ensues is a court drama. In the court, children's and parents equally dejected, worried and melancholic. They think that, have we lost our children in the pursuit of worldly pleasure? Have we alienated them so much that they no longer trust their own family?

Sushanto and Ritesh Mishra are found guilty of possessing and being involved in trafficking dangerous narcotics. They are sentenced ten years imprisonment and fine of three lakhs each. Some of the youth caught during the raid was let off with a fair warning, except the four students of Presidency College, Kolkata Aparajita, Deepanita, Aniket and Siddharth who are declared offenders. 'The Court imposes rigorous imprisonment of three months and a fine of Rs. 1 lakh on each of the convicts except Siddharth. They are first time offenders and have honestly accepted the fact that they travelled from Kolkata to Delhi with the knowledge that they were carrying something suspicious, given to them by the main culprits, but never reported it to the authorities despite getting a few chances to do the same,' the judge justified. 'Each so called parcel weighed about

60gms which is much more than the quantity legally allowed for personal possession.’ ‘ . . . Further to that, all the offenders were also present at the party when the raid was conducted and had consumed small quantities of ‘Ecstasy’, all of which has been proved with prima facie evidence, medical examination and by witnesses (their own parents) present at the party. At the same time, the court also warns all the youths to take this as a fair warning and understand clearly that next time there will be no mercy for offences of such a serious nature.’ ‘Siddharth is however, sentenced to one complete year of rigorous imprisonment and a fine of Rs. 1 lakh for knowing everything yet keeping silent (IPE. 254). So, this book depicts the teenagers especially boys and girls are into an addiction or at wrong path. They spoil their life.

This novel is to full under the genre where teenagers especially females are into an addiction or at wrong path. Life’s not a bed of roses. Every stage has its share of problems. This story expertly brings out the constant tug of war between the Indian youth and their aspirations and the parental expectations. Girls are more than just gender; they have dreams and aspirations and the will and talent to achieve them. This novel brings it out beautifully. It is the story about every element of college life such as, lying to parents for doing something, they get approve of getting a crush on your best friend but unable to express seeing your crush getting into relationship with a friend of yours, how between two girls, one of them is self centered who doesn’t care about feelings of other friend at all, how a boy who might look harmful turns out to be helpful in tough situation, how a course of college trip changes relationship between everyone and brings everyone closer.

CONCLUSION:

The present novel realistically narrates the story of youths.

Over centuries Indian lifestyle has influenced by a lot of changes. Indian people are becoming more modernized and they totally get involved in style. This change affects every type of generation in our country, especially on younger generation. Change in the lifestyle of youth in this ever change world has its impact on our Indian society. Unfortunately, today's youth get befuddled with modernization, westernization and globalization. Today's generation does not realize that where they are heading to. They live a lavish life. Today's young generation is indulging in drugs. This is a youthful and engaging story of teenagers. All the classmates lie or hide things from their parents and want total freedom. But unfortunately, they encounter drug peddlers who intend to use them as pawns for supplying drugs. The above discussion proves that adopting modern lifestyle and value patterns will surely destruct our country. So, it is big challenge for modern India to guide youth in right direction and uses youth power for building a strong nation. The present novel highlights the importance of parents in our life. Also it beautifully raised voice for youths to get rid of their addiction through a strong social message, which is reality check on today's generation.

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The Authors have no conflict of interest to declare that they are relevant to the content of this article.

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